

EFFECTS OF INSTRUCTIONAL VIDEO MATERIALS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 4 LEARNERS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. This study aimed to evaluate the effects of instructional video materials on the performance of Grade 4 learners in English in Sapang Elementary School for the School Year 2021-2022. The quasi-experimental research design was employed in this study. It is a research design where a comparison is made, as in an experiment, but no random assignment of participants to a group occurs. The behavior of the respondents is measured both before and after a treatment or condition is implemented. Quasi-experimental research “resembles” experimental research, but is not true experimental research. Although the independent variable is manipulated, participants or the respondents are not randomly assigned to conditions or order of conditions (Cook and Campbell 2017). The learners in the control group obtained a mean of 23.54 and an MPS of 8.85 while the experimental group had a mean of 30.08 and an MPS of 75.20 in their post-test. Both groups improved in their performance but the performance of the experimental group was much higher than the control group with the former being exposed to the use of instructional video materials.

Keywords. Instructional Video Material, Performance level, Printed Modular Materials

1 Introduction

Modular distance learning involves printed modular materials, these are printed materials that are self-contained units or packages of study materials for use by individuals and provide learning activities to learners. The printed modular materials are in place to address the needs, situations, and resources of each learner and will cover all the bases in ensuring that basic education will be accessible amid the present crisis posed by COVID-19 (The Summit Express 2020).

However, learners today are undeniably exposed to technology. The majority of the kids know and are well-adapted to gadgets and online games. This fact poses a challenge to teachers to learn to adapt to the culture and environment of their learners who are also called digital natives (Aquino, 2019). Choosing modular instruction is also a challenge to both parents and learners especially those who are in the lower class, they can't assist or help their children in answering their modules because the parents themselves hardly understand even the simple instructions.

To attend to the needs of the learner's so-called digital natives, one of the learning delivery modalities that the Department of Education (DepEd) offers to use is radio or TV-based instruction. Instructional video materials are lessons recorded by a teacher teaching a particular subject matter to help learners understand more their lessons. To cope-up with the techy world of the learners, the education department has launched DepEd TV - a program that converts printed modular materials into instructional video materials that can be accessed through the DepEd TV YouTube channel and Facebook page who underwent training on how to effectively deliver lessons via pre-recorded videos. (Cantiga, 2020).

Introducing a lesson to the learners through video presentation gives learners the freedom over how, when, and where they learn and engage them with the video content in the way that suits them best (Lesley University 2021). By using instructional video materials, teachers can keep learners engaged in new and innovative ways. Instructional video materials can change the education landscape by harnessing the power of technology to deliver information better to today's digital natives (Manila Standard, 2020).

The researcher believes that one of the subjects that the pupils experience difficulty in understanding their lesson is English. Language is the foundation of all human relationships. All human relationships are established on the ability of people to communicate effectively with each other. Our thoughts, values, and understandings are developed and expressed through language. This process allows learners to understand better the world in which they live and contributes to the development of their perspectives on the global community. People use language to make sense of and

bring order to their world. Therefore, proficiency in the language enables people to access, process, and keep abreast of information, to engage with wider and more diverse communities, and to learn about the role of language in their own lives, and in their own other cultures (K to 12 English Curriculum Guide, May 2016).

Learners often face difficulty when they learn a second language, especially English. It is caused by the differences in structure between the first language and the second language. Learners sometimes have less concentration. Therefore, they often feel bored during the monotonous learning process. Besides that, learners have difficulty remembering new vocabulary. These cases make learners not interested in the learning process

2 Review of Related Literature

Multimedia materials have become commonly available as resources for learning and instruction, especially due to the increasing use of technology in education. Even though many people associate the term "multimedia" with the use of flashy technology such as interactive dynamic visualizations, in research on learning multimedia term refers to any combination of explanatory spoken or written text and illustrations such as static pictures, diagrams, or animations – some of which can, however, only be implemented by using technology (Schwan, 2017)

Modular instruction is one of the latest innovations in the educational system. This innovation in the modular approach contains a series of activities each of which starts with teaching instructions addressed to the learners, explanations, exercises, and generalizations. A module is defined as a self-contained, independent unit of a planned series of learning activities designed to help the student accomplish certain well-defined objectives. (Guido, 2018)

On the other hand, Paidan, an elementary teacher, pointed out in her interview that the bigger problem they have is that modular learning will not work for some of their pupils. After all, aside from they can't read and comprehend on their own, their parents are also not capable of guiding them because they too are not capable of reading with comprehension. (Perez, 2020)

In the study conducted by (Kosterelioglu 2017), findings show students emphasized the positive effects of using video clips as arousing interest in the class (11.9%), concentrating during class (8.9%), improving memory in learning (27%) and providing intelligibility of the topic (7.9%). (Kayaoglu, et al., 2017) conducted a study entitled "A Small Scale Experimental Study: Using Animations to Learn Vocabulary". In this study, an attempt was made to investigate whether a difference exists between learning vocabulary via animation and traditional paper-based methods.

In the study conducted (Chen, 2018) on the "Effect of Different Multimedia Materials on Learning Performance", he used three different multimedia materials, static multimedia materials, video-based multimedia materials, and animated interactive multimedia material. They were presented to verbalizers and visualizers to investigate how different multimedia materials affect learning performance. Experimental results showed that video-based multimedia material generates the best learning performance for verbalizers. Moreover, dynamic multimedia materials containing video and animation are more appropriate for visualizers than static multimedia materials containing text and images.

The present study is different from other studies reviewed since it has different subjects and locale. On the other hand, the studies of (Almurashi, 2016), (Kosterelioglu, 2016), (Aquino, 2019), (Flores, 2018), and (Kayaoglu, et al., 2017) have similarities with the present study because studies mentioned the use of technology and multimedia integration and effective use of YouTube videos in teaching English. The same is true with the study of (Wang, 2016), (Resngit, 2016), (Basilan, 2018), (Mendiguarin, 2017), and (Chen, 2018) because these studies were concerned with the use of technology especially multimedia since multimedia includes instructional video materials that could improve and enhance the performance of the learners. The above studies used an experimental method that is similar to the present study. Though they differ in terms of topic, they also administered pre-tests, before the use of multimedia instruction and post-tests after to gauge the effectiveness of the multimedia instruction including instructional video materials.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The researcher made use of the quasi-experimental method of research. It is a research design where a comparison is made, as in an experiment, but no random assignment of participants to a group occurs. The behavior of the respondents is measured both before and after a treatment or condition is implemented. Quasi-experimental research “resembles” experimental research, but is not true experimental research. Although the independent variable is manipulated, participants or the respondents are not randomly assigned to conditions or order of conditions (Cook and Campbell 2017).

To ascertain the significant difference that exists between the performance levels of two groups namely, the control group, (the group which is exposed to printed modular materials), and the experimental group, (the group exposed to instructional video materials), a pre-test and post-test were administered by the researcher to both groups of pupils.

3.2 Sources of Data

The subjects of the study were the Grade 4 learners handled by the researcher in English at Sapang Elementary School during the school year 2021-2022. The researcher handled 1 section, Grade 4 – Gabriel which is grouped heterogeneously. The researcher divided the number of respondents according to their class standing and employed the toss coin method to determine the control group and the experimental group. The primary sources of data were the Grade 4 learners of Sapang Elementary School. Their performance in English was tested using instructional video materials and their effectiveness. The researcher used the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in English 4.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To answer sub-problems 1 and 3, mean and mean percentage scores (MPS) were used to determine the learners’ performance in the pre-test and post-test. To answer sub-problem 2 and 4 t-test for independent samples with correlated means was employed. T-test for dependent samples with uncorrelated means was used to answer sub-problem 5.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Performance of the Grade 4 Learners in English in the Pre-test Results

The researcher administered a pre-test to both groups of Grade 4 learners (Control and Experimental) before the exposure to printed modular materials and instructional video materials in English during the first quarter. Table 2 presents the findings of the study

Table 2. Pre-test Results of Control and Experimental Group in English 4
N=26

Group	Mean	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	Descriptive Equivalent
Control	17.85	44.62	AM
Experimental	17.23	43.08	AM

It could be gleaned that the control group obtained a mean score of 17.85 with a mean percentage score of 44.62 while the experimental group obtained a mean score of 17.23 with a mean percentage score of 43.08. It also reflects that both the control and experimental groups obtained almost the same means in the pre-test administered by the researcher. Whereas, as to the mean percentage scores both groups obtained way below the Department of Education's prescribed mastery level of 75%. It could be deduced that there is a need to improve the performance of the Grade 4 learners in English. To improve their performance, they must be properly guided and be provided with plenty of instructional video materials which will be of great help to the performance of Grade 4 learners in English.

4.2 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre-test

Table 3 shows that the respondents registered a mean difference of 0.62. This further shows that the t-computed value of 0.509 is less than the critical t-value which is 2.064. The recorded data reveals that based on the following, there is no significant difference in the performance of the two groups in the pre-test. This means that the two groups have a low level of performance during the pre-test. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted using the p-values since its significant value which is 0.615 is greater than the p critical value < 0.05 . The findings of this study reveal that there is a need to employ strategies to improve the performance of Grade 4 learners in English.

Table 3. Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre-test
N=26

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significant Value (p value)	Decision
Control	17.85	0.62	0.509	0.615	Ho is accepted
Experimental	17.23				

Critical t-value = 2.064, significant at $p < 0.05$, $df = 24$

4.3 Performance of Grade 4 Learners in English in the Post-Test Results

Table 4 shows that the learners in the control group obtained a mean score of 23.54 in the post-test in English 4. The Mean Percentage Score of this group exposed to the use of printed modular materials is 58.85. The learners in the experimental group obtained a mean score of 30.08 in the post-test in English 4 and the computed Mean Percentage Score of this group exposed to instructional video materials is 75.19. It can be observed that both groups demonstrated a marked increase in their performance in the post-test. The data further shows that learners could still learn well when exposed to printed modular materials, but they could gain significant learning when they are exposed to instructional video materials.

The Mean Percentage Score of the control group is still way below the Department of Education's mastery level of 75% while the experimental group's Mean Percentage Score reached the 75% mastery level.

Table 4. Post-Test Results of the Control and Experimental Group in English 4

Group	Mean	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	Descriptive Equivalent
Control	23.54	58.85	MTM
Experimental	30.08	75.19	CAM

4.4 Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Post-Test

Table 5 shows the test of significance of the difference in the post-test performance of the control and experimental group in English 4. It could be gleaned from the table that the control group obtained a mean score of 23.54. on the other hand, the experimental group obtained a mean of 30.08. Meanwhile, the mean difference between the two groups is 6.54.

The t-computed value of 9.24 is relatively greater than the critical value of 2.064 which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the performance of the two groups in the post-test. The p-value of 0.00001 which is less than 0.05 supports the conclusion to reject the null hypothesis (Ho). An improvement in the performance of the control group is highly evident but improvement is significantly greater in the experimental group.

Table 5. Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Post-test
N = 26

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significant Value (p value)	Decision
Control	23.54	6.54	9.24	0.001	Ho is Rejected
Experimental	30.08				

Critical t-value = 2.064, significant at $p < 0.05$, $df = 24$

4.5 Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre-Test and Post-Test

Table 6A. Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre-test and Post-test
N = 13

Control Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significant Value (p value)	Decision
Pre-test	17.85	5.69	5.607	0.011	Ho is rejected
Post-test	23.54				

Critical t-value = 2.179, significant at $p < 0.05$, $df = 12$

Table 6A shows the results of the pre-test and post-test administered to the control group. It shows that there is a significant difference in the performance of the members of the said group. It can be gleaned from the table that there is an increase in the post-test mean of 5.69. It means that printed modular materials can still be effective in teaching English but the Mean.

The percentage Score (MPS) of the said group in the post-test is still below the Department of Education's mastery level of 75%. Hence, it may be inferred that there is a significant difference in the performance between the pre-test and post-test. It is also reflected in the table that the t-computed is 5.607 which is greater than the 2.179 critical t-value. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

4.6 Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Experimental Group in the Pre-Test and Post-Test

Meanwhile, Table 6B shows that the pre-test and post-test results of the experimental group also showed improvement in the learners' performance as exposed to instructional video materials. It can be gleaned from the table that there is an increase in the mean scores of the experimental group with a 12.85 mean difference. Hence, it may be inferred that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of the experimental group. This shows that there was a significant improvement obtained by this group after the implementation of the instructional video materials in the experimental group. The group's mean percentage score of 75.19 reached the prescribed 75% mastery level standard set by the Department of Education.

Table 6B. Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Experimental Group in the Pre-test and Post-test
N = 13

Experimental Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significant Value (p value)	Decision
Pre-test	17.23	12.85	18.203	0.001	Ho is rejected
Post-test	30.08				

Critical t-value = 2.179 at 0.05, df = 12

It can be deduced that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the performance of Grade 4 learners in English before and after exposure to instructional video materials in the pre-test and post-test is hereby rejected. The results reflect the noted advantages of using instructional video materials to empower learners and get them engaged in learning. Based on the data, the use of instructional video materials is a contributory factor to learners' academic success truly paving the way for their high level of performance as shown in the post-test results.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The control and experimental groups had a low level of performance in the pre-test. There is no significant difference in the level of performance of the two groups before using the instructional video materials as revealed in the pre-test. The level of performance of the experimental group is higher than the control group based on the post-test results. There is a significant difference in the performance of the control and experimental group in the post-test as both groups were exposed to: (control) printed modular materials and (experimental) instructional video materials. There is a significant difference in the performance of each of the two groups in the pre-test and post-test. The experimental group, after the treatment performed better. The control group performed with minor improvement.

Instructional video materials should be used as they will be of great help to the performance of Grade 4 learners in English. Elementary teachers should be encouraged to employ the use of instructional video materials to help improve the performance of Learners in English 4. Instructional video materials should be adopted to help facilitate better learning outcomes. Teachers should explore and use a variety of approaches that can help to improve learners' performance. Similar studies should be conducted using other learning areas.

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